

Machine Learning for Biomaterial Printing

Examples, Opportunities and Challenges

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ABSTRACT

Biomaterial 3D printing is the process of creating 3D structures mostly by layer-by-layer deposition using a printer. It utilizes materials such as cells, polymers, and ceramics to mimic the properties of natural tissues and organs and is a rapidly emerging field that holds great promise to produce personalized medical devices, tissues, and organs. Machine learning has the potential to revolutionize the field of biomaterial 3D printing. This paper serves as a review of current research on machine learning in biomaterial 3D printing. By using machine learning algorithms, it is possible to optimize the design and production of biomaterials for specific applications, such as tissue engineering and drug delivery. For example, machine learning can be used to predict the mechanical properties of a biomaterial based on its composition or to optimize the microstructure of a biomaterial for improved performance. This can help researchers elucidate relationships between compositions and properties. Additionally, machine learning can be used to plan and control the 3D printing process itself, allowing for the production of highly complex and customized biomaterial structures. Even post-printing processes can be optimized allowing for more efficient and consistent production of 3D printed constructs. Current challenges are similar to challenges in other fields of artificial intelligence. Examples are problems with data acquisition, quality, and the lack of standardized approaches for easier comparison. Overall, the integration of machine learning into biomaterial 3D printing holds great promise for the development of advanced medical therapies and devices.

KEYWORDS

3D printing, biomaterials, machine learning, medical application, process optimization

1 Introduction

3D printing or additive manufacturing (AM) provides possibilities to create custom made, unique shapes and forms for specific purposes. In general, 3D printing is characterized by recreating a digital 3D model by layer-by-layer deposition of a desired material. One important field of application is biomaterial printing, where 3D printed medical devices or artificial tissue can

be tailored to a patient or a treatment [15]. Artificial tissue could for example help overcome the donor organ shortage, lead to reduced waiting times for transplantations and reduce rejection responses. The printing process as well as the pre- and postprocessing is complex and requires extreme precision in order to fit an equally complex human body [10]. Advanced computational techniques such as machine learning (ML) facilitate the elaborate development of biomaterials and can assist in experiment planning as well as in the prediction of properties, especially toxicity in medical applications. Additionally, long term effects like material stability must be treated in a targeted manner during development and production [15].

3D printing can be an expensive and time-consuming procedure because it is supposed to produce one perfect output in contrast to mass production. If done correctly, 3D printing is very efficient in material usage, since no scrap is produced. The monitoring of the production process is therefore extremely important. ML can help point out irregularities at an early stage. It can be even more effective to apply ML resources to optimize the 3D printing process in order to avoid production problems and errors in general [10].

In the following abstracts, research on ML applications for the optimization of different stages of biomaterial printing is presented and discussed.

2 Methods

A literature review was conducted by searching for “biomaterial printing machine learning” in Google Scholar (<https://scholar.google.com/>). Papers from at least 2020 onwards with at least 20 citations were collected when the topic was focused on biomaterial development for 3D printing and all further stages of the printing. Papers mentioned in reviews were not checked regarding the number of citations.

3 Results

Several papers already sum up previous research efforts in specific stages of biomaterial 3D printing or focus on specific use cases. The results of this review are presented regarding the processing stages to compare similar approaches and create an

overview understanding. Note that in the following the term model can mean a ML model, which is essentially a mathematical model, but also a 3D shape, which is a digital template for the printing process.

3.1 Machine Learning for Biomaterial development

Most biomaterials are not natively suitable for depositing and printing since for printing certain flow properties are necessary, but the material needs to be stable soon after printing. During printing a certain shape must be retained. To a limited extent the printing process can be adjusted to the material, but the mentioned properties must be roughly given. Here biomaterial development comes into play:

Nadernezhad & Groll tried to create an ML solution to classify biomaterial mixtures as printable and non-printable and explain the outcomes via Shapley values. They showed that the printability could be predicted on basis of the rheological properties, meaning the flow properties, of the materials. The researchers used a random forest classifier for binary classification (printable and non-printable) with the Boruta all-relevant feature selection method. Furthermore, Shapley values were calculated by n-repeated k-fold cross-validation of the trained ML model. The Shapley values show which rheological properties are the most important and explain why some materials can be printed better than others [9]. Figure 1 shows the research process. This work is mainly fundamental research and can facilitate biomaterial development by helping in the initial screening of materials via their rheological properties. For the in-depth development or for screening significantly different materials however, this ML model might not be useful, because extensive rheological testing is needed to either adjust the model or create the necessary input features for the model. In this case even more effective to directly test the printability straight away.

Suwardi et al. sum up the current efforts to develop polymer and metallic materials for printing. They also describe very specific ML models which mostly help solve a subproblem of material development, such as the prediction of formation of a gel,

foreign body response or composition–structure–properties. For the prediction of gel formation, a gradient boosting algorithm was preferred to a random forest and logistic regression. For the discovery of composition–structure–properties and therefore the prediction of material properties a support vector machine (SVM) algorithm with a radial-based kernel function and an artificial neural network (ANN) can be used: While the predictions with SVM still need electronic properties as an input, the ANN approach only needs the composition of the elements in the alloy to directly predict the Young's modulus (measure of elasticity) [15, 16]. ANNs are the most often mentioned algorithms in the review also for failure prediction. However, details and advantages of architecture are not discussed. Furthermore, Suwardi et al. refer to the work from related fields such as aircraft material development for predicting material failure and durability, still without mentioning details. In general, they conclude that some of the ML techniques mentioned can contribute greatly to the development of new biomaterials by predicting result which would otherwise have to be obtained from complex experiments [15].

3.2 Machine Learning for Printing Preparation

An important preprocessing step in some medical applications of 3D printing is to acquire a high-resolution 3D model of the organ, tissue or bone that needs to be replaced. Ng et al. state that there is a gap between the needed resolution for these models and medical imaging. There are already neural network (NN) models called super-resolution that can produce a higher resolution than the original image has. Training for such networks is done by down sampling high resolution images. The NN then has to learn to create the original high-resolution images as an output from the artificial low-resolution input. Similar techniques can also help reduce the amount of 2D image segments that are needed for a complete 3D image [10].

The related application of ML would be to analyze medical images to cut out only the desired organ or tissue. Several ML algorithms can be used for this task and object detection is already

Figure 1: Research process of Nadernezhad & Groll [9]. Different formulations were tested regarding rheological properties and printability. The results were used to build a model to predict printability from the rheological properties. As a last step, the influence of the different rheological properties was determined by Shapley values.

extensively used in other fields. Roth et al use an approach with two 3D fully convolutional networks (FCN), where in the first stage rough candidate regions are predicted while the second stage identifies the target organ within those regions. The authors state that for some use cases 2D FCNs might be sufficient [12].

In the case that living cells are involved in the printing it is important to monitor the cell viability. A ML approach to this problem could be camera image monitoring and classification. For this a model that is trained on different camera streams with contaminated and non-contaminated cultures could be used. There are several other approaches for cell culture analyses based on easy measurements like PCR analysis and supervised deep learning with labelled data [10].

ML techniques can also help inexperienced users in designing 3D printing models called computer-aided design (CAD) models. Proposed applications are identification of suitable design features as well as identification of designs that might not be possible to print. Most of the proposed models are ANN because they outperform simple linear models due to higher flexibility [5]. Although some of the proposed models are highly specific, existing models for CAD optimization from other fields could be used in biomaterial printing as well and might already be part of some CAD software packages.

3.3 Machine Learning for Printing Optimization

During the printing phase, material needs to be deposited accurately on the correct spot. If the flow properties of the material are suitable for printing, further important process parameters are printing speed, flow rate and nozzle/printing diameter [14]. Some aspects of rheology and flow optimization in 3D printing are already well understood and can be explained by more or less complex formulars that do not need machine learning to be computed. In combination with biomaterials and possibly even functional cells, the relationships between printing parameters and desired outcome are becoming more complex. Ng et al. propose a deep learning model to predict the outcome for different printing parameters as input. Since explaining the influences of the printing parameters on the outcomes will still be desired, the authors suggest proven methods for the interpretation of the deep learning models as post hoc analysis [10]. Another

Figure 2: Optimization of the printing process by labelling ideal and bad extrusion [3].

approach from the same authors would be reinforcement learning, where the intended outcome (accurate printing, high cell viability) would determine reward. Wu and Xu showed that even less complex algorithms like random forest, xgboost, Lasso regression and support vector regression are suitable for predicting droplet volume and droplet velocity in bioprinting. Their results show that xgboost and an ensemble of all mentioned algorithms achieve the highest performance [17].

Figure 2 shows how the printing process can be monitored and optimized continuously during printing with computer vision. When the printing should be automatically monitored through camera images, a Convolutional neural network (CNN) can be trained on images as shown in figure 2: images need to be labelled with desired and undesired outcomes e.g., ideal vs under- and over extrusion. If a strategy for resolving problems is included in the printing program, corrective actions can be taken automatically. A corrective action might be the reduction in printing velocity when under extrusion occurs [10]. Depending on the material, also other imaging methods like near-infrared thermal CMOS cameras, photodiodes, and x-ray phase-contrast imaging could be used [5].

Similarly, anomaly detection to identify problematic regions in the printed product was attempted by several researchers. Although the research is not specific for biomaterial printing, the results will be summarized here as an opportunity for all 3D printing fields. Goh et al. state that most anomaly detection methods are based on computer vision and CNNs, although other algorithms were also tested. Other algorithms range from bag of words (BoW) classification, k-nearest-neighbor (KNN) and reinforcement learning, whereby CNNs achieve the highest classification accuracies. As a disadvantage of CNNs, their long runtime is mentioned [5].

3.4 Machine Learning for Post-Processing

Especially when functioning organs and cells are printed, the complex process is not finished by depositing the material. The tissue needs to mature in a well-defined medium even assisted with stimuli. Like the development of the printing material, medium development traditionally is a trial-and-error method and very time consuming. Ng et al. propose supervised deep learning to formulate culture media if data from an organ-on-chip-setup are available. For both culture media and growth stimuli planning the authors propose reinforcement learning but do not give concrete examples [10].

3.5 Current challenges of Machine Learning for Biomaterial Printing

Problems that arise with ML for biomaterial printing are of course similar to general ML problems. More specifically, problems with data availability and variability arise due to the narrow field of research and its biomedical nature [4].

The limited amount of data leads to the problem that sophisticated, more training intensive methods of ML, such as complex ANN architectures, cannot always be applied. Biomaterial printing itself, however, is a complex problem often

with multi-objective optimization. The optimum of data amount, quality and complexity of the method needs to be found to achieve good results. New methods in ML like transfer learning could facilitate the problem of data amount and training. In transfer learning, pretrained models are used. The concluding training of the models does not require as much data as training a model from scratch. For example, first attempts have been made to transfer knowledge from the prediction of pure material properties to the properties of a composite [11][18].

Finally, the safety and ethics challenge must be mentioned. If biomaterial printing is used to engineer organs or medication specifically for one patient, ethics and data protection are a major issue. Medical patient data needs to be stored safely and sharing of data might not be easily possible. The printed medication or device must work well in all cases, fit the patients' body perfectly and ensure long health without adverse effects. In case of failure, the question of responsibility arises. Strategies need to be found to deal with these questions [3].

4 Discussion

As shown in the results section, there are a variety of different, very specific applications of ML in all stages of biomaterial printing. Many ML solutions are derived from other scientific fields with several refined solutions that are specifically tailored to biomaterial printing. Unfortunately, some authors, especially in the context of reviews, do only describe the rough framework of a ML solution and others do not state why they did use a certain ML algorithm, which makes comparison difficult. In summary it seems like researchers in this field focus more on computationally expensive but very accurate and powerful solutions. Various forms of ANN were mentioned for almost all applications. This is understandable because here we operate in a very complex and elaborate field of research in which workpieces require the highest level of precision. Due to the digital background of 3D printing, many researchers probably have sufficient computational resources at their disposal. In addition, the simplification of the ML solutions for smaller companies and even private users might be beyond question. Goh et al. conclude that in the future even more advanced ML techniques should be used but techniques still need to be efficient for use cases, like printing monitoring, where fast feedback is needed [5].

Depending on the research questions of the paper, the authors also focus on explainability and interpretability of the ML model to gain more insights in the physical and chemical mechanisms that are involved in the process [9]. For some models such as computer vision solutions for the monitoring of the printing process, interpretability might not be as important, if the process is working well. Here, continuous monitoring of the model quality itself might be crucial to adapt the model to changing conditions. On the other hand, prediction of toxicity might be important to be explainable and consequently understood by researchers to not make fatal false predictions. Ng et al. promote interpretability in deep learning for biomaterial printing to strengthen the trust in these powerful methods [10].

Another focus of some papers is the optimization of ML techniques in respect to the available training data. Wu et al. for example chose the neural-network machine "βLow" because it performed well with a small training data set (only 164 samples) [16]. As an option for optimization of the ML process, feature tuning was mentioned in the literature found. An example can be reducing the features to only the significant ones [9].

Since the ML applications mentioned are very different it is not possible to find the one best algorithms or ANN architecture for biomaterial printing. Generally, for developing an ML solution for biomaterial printing, a very good domain knowledge is needed to produce the desired results. Ideally, computer engineers are involved in data acquisition and model creation at an early stage and work together closely with domain experts. Once a valid model is created however, even less qualified personnel might be able to handle biomaterial printing processes [5, 15].

Future challenges for 3D bioprinting can be derived from the sheer amount of research approaches mentioned in the results and the cited reviews. In order to optimize the development of ML solutions itself, standardization is needed to facilitate comparison between the various scientific works. This may include using the same metrics and the sharing of code and additional materials. Another aspect is that most ML solutions profit from bigger datasets. In some research fields, sharing and publishing data is very common but especially in the development of printing materials, details on compositions and properties are treated confidentially to keep the business advantage. If cooperation and reuse of code and data is facilitated and rewarded, new breakthroughs can be achieved in this important discipline [10, 15]. The application of transfer learning for biomaterial printing would also profit from standardization and data scaling [13]. Researchers propose to use advanced ML, the combination of traditional physics models, and digital twin for improved transferability [1].

To improve standardization in this field, a board of trustees like the ITU/WHO Focus Group on Artificial Intelligence for Health could be built [7]. This group would need to take care of the development of shared repositories, data, standard pipelines, libraries and APIs specialized for ML in biomaterial printing.

Regarding ethical and safety challenges, researchers will need to orientate themselves on existing strategies and guidelines from the medical field. Strategies like federated learning could protect patients' data [6]. The FDA already provides a guideline on artificial intelligence and machine learning in software as a medical device [2].

5 Conclusion

3d biomaterial printing is well suited to be supported by ML because it is a digital field, and the complexity requires safe and fast methods for optimization. All stages of printing can be facilitated with ML with all kinds of algorithms and techniques. ML was used in the biomaterial discovery phase as well as the manufacturing process and postprocessing. ML is also often used to speed up the research itself and secure new insides and useful

medical applications. ANN were mentioned most of the time but also ensemble methods and tree-based models were used. For big data sets without sufficient labelling, reinforcement learning was used. Depending on the goals of the ML solution, the focus is on accuracy, speed, interpretability or different other aspects. Domain knowledge is needed for the very specific applications as well as collaboration between researchers and companies. Open-source initiatives that standardize procedures and algorithms or facilitate data sharing will improve these collaborations. MIT and BASF for example created an open source solution for optimal experiment design [8].

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